

Vitiligo: Etiology and Cure

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Abstract

Vitiligo is considered a chronic autoimmune disorder characterized by progressive depigmentation resulting from the loss of melanocytes in Western medicine. Although its exact pathogenesis remains uncertain, modern medicine identifies genetic predisposition, immune system dysfunction, and environmental factors as key contributors. Conventional treatments often fail to provide lasting results. Emerging therapies, such as the holistic approach offered by Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, present alternative perspectives on managing skin diseases. Our previous reports propose that skin conditions, including eczema, psoriasis, chronic urticaria, and dyshidrosis are karmic and spiritual in origin. This paper examines the etiology of vitiligo and explores the potential role of spiritual healing in its management. Our findings suggest that vitiligo's underlying cause is tied to karma, particularly killing karma. By addressing and eliminating this karma, patients have restored their skin health. This study suggests that Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is effective in curing vitiligo, improving patients' quality of life, particularly their psychological well-being.

Key Words: *Vitiligo, Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, Killing Karma, Spiritual healing, Buddhist practice*

Introduction

In Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), the name of vitiligo (白癜風) originates from the term "white patches (白癜)" on the skin. It is associated with the concept of "wind (風)" in TCM, as its onset is unpredictable, spreading like wheals and causing depigmentation wherever the "wind" moves.

In Western medicine, vitiligo is considered a prevalent autoimmune skin disorder characterized by progressive depigmented patches of the skin and/or mucosa [1]. This condition arises from the gradual loss of melanocytes, the pigment-producing cells in the skin, leading to the appearance of white, depigmented areas.

Affecting approximately 0.5% to 2% of the global population [2], vitiligo transcends ethnic, gender, and geographic boundaries. It often poses a substantial cosmetic and psychosocial burden on those affected, impacting their quality of life and emotional well-being [3-5].

While conventional therapies, such as phototherapy, corticosteroids, and immunosuppressants, can

provide some relief, their effects are often partial and temporary, with a high likelihood of recurrence once treatment is discontinued [6]. Various surgical interventions have been widely incorporated into combination therapies. Melanocyte regeneration and activation therapies hold promise for effectively addressing the condition. For patients with refractory vitiligo, psychological monitoring and interventions are crucial to mitigate the pathogenic effects of chronic stress. Finally, depigmentation techniques and camouflage methods can help achieve a uniform skin tone and enhance the quality of life for affected individuals [7].

Despite various treatment options, vitiligo remains one of the most challenging conditions in dermatology [8]. This is because scientists have not correctly identified its root cause. As a result, current treatments focus on managing symptoms rather than addressing the underlying cause, making complete eradication impossible.

Our previous reports propose that skin diseases are karmic and spiritual conditions, which can be effectively addressed through the practice of the

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Three (or Four or Five) Golden Buddhist Practices of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. In this study, we aimed to evaluate the potential of this Dharma approach in the treatment of vitiligo.

Etiology

In the scientific community, the pathogenesis of vitiligo is widely considered to be complex, involving an interplay of genetic predisposition and environmental triggers [6]. Some researchers propose that vitiligo has a multifactorial etiology, primarily driven by a T-cell-mediated autoimmune response targeting cutaneous melanocytes [9]. Others suggest that the etiopathogenesis is obscure but likely involves multiple contributing factors, such as oxidative stress, inflammation, genetics, and autoimmunity [10]. Despite considerable advancements in understanding vitiligo, its exact causes and mechanisms remain elusive [8]. In summary, the lack of a definitive understanding of vitiligo's etiology and pathogenesis continues to hinder the development of a curative treatment.

Our previous reports suggest that skin diseases are karmic in nature. When karma flares up, it can develop into spiritual diseases, leading to harm to the skin. This theory has been validated in cases of eczema [11,12], psoriasis [11], chronic urticaria [13], and dyshidrosis [14]. In this study, we aim to explore whether this theory extends to vitiligo and evaluate the effectiveness of the Dharma method in treating the condition.

The following are five Dharma Q&A dialogues in which Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu answered questions from callers or inquirers. Through these exchanges, we can gain insight into the Dharma perspective on the causes of vitiligo.

Q&A 1. Vitiligo and psoriasis are karmic illnesses caused by killing karma (excerpt) [15]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Jan. 8, 2013.)

Caller: Hello, Master Lu. I was born in 1986, the Year of the Tiger. Could you check my health, please?

Master: You need to pay special attention to your throat; it's in poor condition.

Caller: And what about my skin?

Master: Your skin issues are mainly on the back of your hands, around your neck, and on your stomach.

Caller: That is right.

Master: When you were young, you ate too many live animals, and your skin still contains karmic imprints from the chickens you killed.

Caller: I am quite afraid of killing chickens, but I think

I might have killed some before.

Master: If you have killed chickens, you cannot escape the karmic consequences.

Caller: I have had vitiligo and psoriasis since I was a child.

Master: These are karmic illnesses.

Caller: I have been practicing Buddhism for five months now. How many Little Houses will I need?

Master: 49 Little Houses.

Caller: I have already offered more than 50 Little Houses for my karmic creditors. I made a vow to offer the first batch of 49 Little Houses to my karmic creditors.

Master: Very good, no problem.

Caller: Master Lu, could you help me adjust my daily practice? My current daily recitation includes:

Great Compassion Mantra: 21 times,

Heart Sutra: 49 times,

Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance: 5 times,

Cundi Dharani: 49 times,

Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra: 49 times,

Da Ji Xiang Tian Nü Zhou: 21 times,

Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots: 21 times,

Xiao Zai Ji Xiang Shen Zhou: 21 times.

Master: That is fine; no major issues.

Q&A 2. Vitiligo caused by lack of filial piety in a past life: How to resolve it through scripture recitation [16]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Oct. 24, 2015.)

Caller: Master Lu, I am so surprised! I never imagined that I would come to know about Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door just two days ago, thanks to a fellow practitioner who introduced me to you.

Master: Do you know that we have over ten million followers? They often give up their chances to call in so that new practitioners like you can reach me. You must practice diligently; otherwise, how could you get through? This is meant to encourage you.

Caller: Thank you, Master. I am truly grateful. Here is the situation: I firmly believe in this Dharma Door and that it can transform my life. However, I have a significant karmic obstacle that I need your guidance on. I was diagnosed with vitiligo at the age of 5, and now I am 33 years old.

Master: Have you started reciting Little Houses yet?

Caller: Not yet.

Master: If you have not, then nothing will work. You must start reciting Little Houses immediately. Calling

me alone will not solve the problem. When you have offered enough Little Houses to your karmic creditors, your vitiligo will improve significantly. Even cancer can be cured through recitation, so what is vitiligo in comparison?

Caller: But I was hoping you could advise me on how many Little Houses I would need to resolve this karmic obstacle.

Master: Keep reciting. This condition did not develop overnight, and it is a karmic illness.

Caller: I understand.

Master: Karmic illnesses cannot be resolved with just a few Little Houses. To see about a 40% improvement in your condition, you'll need at least 400 Little Houses to start with. Additionally, if you make a vow to become fully vegetarian, your condition will improve even faster.

Caller: I have already been fully vegetarian for four months.

Master: Then why haven't you started reciting Little Houses?

Caller: I only came to know about Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door two days ago.

Master: But how did you decide to become vegetarian earlier?

Caller: On June 27 of this year, I encountered Buddhism and attended a seven-day Buddhist retreat at NSH Temple. From that point onward, I became fully vegetarian.

Master: That shows you have a strong affinity with Buddhism, and now is the right time for you to awaken. It is wonderful that you have come to know about Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. From now on, you must dedicate yourself to learning Buddhism and improving yourself. Let me tell you this: vitiligo is caused by a lack of filial piety toward your parents in your past life. That's why, no matter how good you are to your parents in this life, they may not treat you particularly well in return. Do you understand?

Caller: Yes, that resolves the knot in my heart.

Q&A 3. Vitiligo is caused by excessive fish consumption [17]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on June 9, 2020.)

Caller: Hello, Master! I would like to ask about a woman born in 1971, in the Year of the Pig. She has a skin condition.

Master: Her body is full of fish; she ate too much fish in the past.

Caller: She has vitiligo.

Master: Yes, vitiligo is caused by this issue. Tell her

to use a specific ointment and also recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*. She should vow to recite it 10,000 times.

Caller: But she follows a different Dharma Door.

Master: Then there is nothing I can do. You can tell her that if she is willing to practice Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and inform Nanjing Bodhisattva, it might help.

Caller: Okay.

Master: Have her try it. If she recovers suddenly, she will realize the benefits. Actually, all Dharma Doors are good; it is just about finding the one that suits you best, right?

Caller: Right.

Master: All doctors are good because they save lives. If one doctor can not treat your condition, you can try another. There's nothing wrong with that.

Caller: True.

Master: Just do not say the doctor is bad. Every doctor is trying to help you.

Caller: I agree. Does she have any other issues? The vitiligo does not affect her much since she has had it for so many years.

Master: It does not have a significant impact, but it's embarrassing for her. It is negative karma. Eating too many live beings causes her to lose face.

Caller: I see.

Master: She also has joint problems, back issues, and her left kidney is not in good condition.

Caller: I wasn't aware of that.

Master: Tell her to be cautious. Her cervical spine is also problematic. She experiences hair loss, and she has had insomnia in the past.

Caller: That's correct.

Q&A 4. Harming others in a past life and heavy killing karma in this life led to vitiligo [18]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Sept. 1, 2015.)

Caller: Hello, Master! I pay my respects to you, Master, and thank you for your hard work! Today, they take full responsibility for the karmic consequences related to the questions I am asking on their behalf. Master, could you please check on a 1951 female born in the Year of the Rabbit? Does she have any spirits on her body? How much karma does she carry?

Master: There is a spirit on her body.

Caller: How many Little Houses are needed?

Master: 27. It is a female spirit, with both eyebrows

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standing upright and curling upwards at the ends.

Caller: Oh. How much karma does she have?

Master: 24%.

Caller: How is her physical health?

Master: Her health is poor, very weak. Her back, cervical spine, and lower back are all in bad condition.

Caller: Also, Master, she has vitiligo. The white patches have spread to her face, especially her forehead. Is this due to karma?

Master: Yes, it is karmic. Let me see... It is caused by two factors: First, in her past life, she harmed others. Second, in this life, she has accumulated heavy killing karma. That is why the retribution has manifested visibly on her face.

Caller: How many Little Houses should she vow to recite, and how many fish should she liberate?

Master: She needs to recite 590 Little Houses and liberate 20,000 fish.

Caller: Okay, thank you very much, Master.

Q&A 5. Children developing vitiligo is related to family killing karma [19]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on June 28, 2015.)

Caller: Hello, Master! Is it true that children developing vitiligo are generally related to the family's killing karma?

Master: Yes.

Caller: Thank you, Master, for your guidance.

The five Q&A Dharma dialogues from Dharma Master Lu attribute vitiligo to karmic consequences, similar to other skin diseases, which also have karmic origins.

Recovery

The following are five Q&A dialogues in which Master Lu directly guided callers and inquirers on how to recover from vitiligo.

Q&A 6. A child's vitiligo is related to killing karma and how to recover from it [20]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Sept. 24, 2019.)

Caller: Hello, Master! Please check on a girl born in 1999, Year of the Rabbit. The child was recently diagnosed with vitiligo. Her mother would like to know how many Little Houses are needed.

Master: It is related to killing karma. Quickly make a vow.

Caller: How many Little Houses are needed?

Master: She needs 65 Little Houses and to recite 100,000 times the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth*

Mantra. Start reciting them now.

Caller: How about life liberation?

Master: She should liberate 1,500 fish.

Caller: Okay.

Master: If this is delayed, there will be problems. Chronic illnesses will surface.

Caller: Understood. Thank you, Master, and thank you, Guan Yin Bodhisattva.

Q&A 7. Vitiligo is a karmic illness requiring the recitation of the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, little houses, and life liberation [21]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Oct. 14, 2012.)

Caller: Hello, Master! I have a friend who practices a certain religion. He has vitiligo, with patches of white on his temples.

Master: This is a karmic illness. Ask him to recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* and offer Little Houses. He should also perform more life liberations.

Q&A 8. A lady suffering from vitiligo and possessed by a female spirit and needing ascending to recover [22]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on March 9, 2013.)

Caller: Hello, Master! I was born in 1967, in the Year of the Sheep. I am a woman, and I would like to know about my karmic debts. Master, I have a skin condition, vitiligo. I currently recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* five times a day and offer 5, 7, or 10 Little Houses to my karmic creditors per week.

Master: I see a woman's face. Her hair is slightly curly and combed back, especially at the temples. Her face is a bit round, her eyes are not large, her height is not tall, and she has a short neck. I am not sure if this woman is you. If it's you, then it's not a spirit.

Caller: That is not me. I am 1.7 meters tall.

Master: Then this woman is the spirit on your body. She resembles someone related to your mother's side of the family.

Caller: How many Little Houses should I offer?

Master: Quite a few—32. Offer them gradually, and she will likely appear in your dreams.

Caller: Got it. For my skin condition, should I start by reciting for this karmic creditor?

Master: Yes.

Caller: While reciting the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, should I say, "Eliminate the karmic debts

that caused my skin condition”?

Master: Yes, you can say that.

Caller: I currently recite it five times a day. Should I increase it?

Master: No need to increase it. How many times do you recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*?

Caller: I used to recite it 49 times, but now I recite it 21 times.

Master: Change it back to 49 times. Also, recite the *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots* 49 times.

Caller: Okay.

Master: Additionally, perform life liberation.

Caller: I release lives every week.

Master: Take some Great Compassion Water from Guan Yin Bodhisattva, use a cotton ball to dab it, and gently apply it to your skin while reciting the *Great Compassion Mantra*.

Caller: Understood.

Q&A 9. Vitiligo will improve after vowing to abstain from eggs [23]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Oct 20, 2020.)

Caller: Hello, Master! I was born in 1973, in the Year of the Ox, and I am a full vegetarian. I would like to ask about my health.

Master: You tend to overthink things.

Caller: Yes, that is true.

Master: You have a righteous character, but you exhibit some traits of autism—you often feel that others have wronged you.

Caller: That is correct.

Master: You treat people very well, but you feel they do not reciprocate.

Caller: Exactly.

Master: You are repaying karmic debts. You need to take care of your health. Your lower back and cervical spine are not in good condition, and you often feel pain and soreness in your neck.

Caller: Yes, that is right.

Master: You are a good person, but you must not get stuck in negative thoughts. Overthinking has already started to affect your digestive system.

Caller: Oh. I turned 46 this year and passed a predestined calamity. How much karma do I still have?

Master: 24%. You are doing well—your karmic obstacles are not that high.

Caller: But I always feel there are many spirits asking

for karmic repayment.

Master: That is true—your karmic obstacles are not high, but you have many spirits asking for repayment. Let me give you a simple analogy: someone might not be bad, but if he owes a lot of debts, it's still problematic, right?

Caller: Oh, I understand. Master, when will my vitiligo improve? I have been reciting scriptures and praying for this.

Master: Are you completely vegetarian?

Caller: Yes, I have been a full vegetarian since March 2018.

Master: Let me check. You are still eating eggs.

Caller: Yes, I still eat eggs and drink milk.

Master: You have been eating a lot of eggs. Milk is fine, but you should stop eating eggs. If you vow to stop eating eggs, your vitiligo will improve within 3-6 months. Additionally, you need to recite two sets of *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* (108 times each) and complete 108 Little Houses for your karmic creditors.

Caller: Thank you, Master.

Q&A 10. Blood issues leading to vitiligo, recite Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra and take TCM [24]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Jan. 14, 2020.)

Caller: Hello, Master! Please take a look at someone born in 1984, in the Year of the Rat. Recently, she has developed many white spots on her face.

Master: Oh dear, this Rat... it is similar to vitiligo.

Caller: Yes, it looks like vitiligo—white patches have appeared.

Master: It is an issue with her blood. Ask her to quickly see a doctor or start taking TCM. She can take *Andrographis paniculata* to cool and detoxify her blood system—it is very effective.

Caller: Alright. Recently, she vowed to recite many *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantras*.

Master: She needs to recite 10,000 times of the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*.

Caller: Got it.

Master: Hurry! Right now, the condition has not fully manifested. If it does, it will look even worse—extremely unpleasant.

From these five dialogues, the key methods for healing from vitiligo include diligently practicing the Golden Buddhist Practices, such as making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life

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liberation. Reciting the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* and offering Little Houses to karmic creditors are essential. Additionally, practicing compassion is emphasized as crucial for healing, with vegetarianism and avoiding harm to sentient beings reflecting this principle. By sincerely following these spiritual practices, individuals seek to resolve karmic debts and restore their health.

Here are 6 cases where practitioners applied this Dharma-based approach to vitiligo treatment. The outcomes are examined below.

Results

Case 1. Healing My Vitiligo Using the Five Golden Buddhist Practices

In 2023, I encountered my predestined "369 calamity." Around mid-March, while combing my hair, I suddenly noticed a small white patch about the size of a fingernail near my hairline on the right side of my forehead. Initially, I did not take it seriously, thinking it was nothing. However, after a couple of days, I checked again and saw that the white patch had grown larger. This made me anxious as I realized it could be vitiligo.

To confirm my suspicion, I visited the dermatology department at the Hospital. After an examination, the doctor diagnosed the white patch on my forehead as vitiligo. The doctor told me that vitiligo is difficult to cure—it is currently a global medical challenge, with no specific medication available to completely treat it. It can only be controlled to prevent further spread. While it does not endanger life, it affects one's appearance and requires significant financial expense during the treatment and recovery process.

Initially, I was frightened, but at the same time, a surge of strength arose within me: I am now practicing Buddhism. I have Guan Yin Bodhisattva as my strong support and a compassionate Master who has brought us such an incredible Dharma Door. With the Five Golden Buddhist Practices of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, what do I have to fear?

I asked the doctor, "Is this a skin disease?" The doctor replied, "Yes." Upon hearing this, my confidence in overcoming vitiligo grew even stronger.

The doctor recommended a specialized vitiligo hospital in the provincial capital and provided its address, phone number, and the name of a specialist. Since there were no specific treatments available at the local hospital, I returned home.

Master Lu has explained: "There are two types of illnesses—physical illnesses and karmic illnesses." He has also taught that skin diseases are karmic

illnesses. Before practicing Buddhism, I had committed acts of killing, such as slaughtering chickens, ducks, and fish. After learning Buddhism and starting to recite Buddhist scriptures, I came to understand the heavy karmic burden of killing and stopped these harmful actions.

The next morning, during the morning incense offering, I prayed to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to help me eliminate the vitiligo on my forehead. I then made the following vows to Guan Yin Bodhisattva:

1. Recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* 10,000 times and the *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots* 10,000 times within 3 months.
2. Recite 3 sets of the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, with each set consisting of 108 recitations, within 3 months.
3. Repay my karmic creditors 300 Little Houses within one year.
4. Perform life liberation for 10,000 fish within one year.
5. Read 100 chapters of *Buddhism in Plain Terms* within 3 months.

After making these vows, I felt much more at ease and began diligently fulfilling them every day.

In addition to my Dharma practice, I also obtained some basic medication from a local clinic to control the spread of vitiligo. At the same time, I found a folk remedy online that involved rubbing the affected area with fresh ginger. I applied both methods simultaneously.

Truly, with sincere effort, the Buddhas respond compassionately! With deep gratitude for Guan Yin Bodhisattva's compassion and the miraculous efficacy of the Five Golden Buddhist Practices, I saw results within just over two months. The vitiligo on my forehead had almost completely disappeared [Figure 1]! I was filled with Dharma joy!

I am deeply grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva and to Master Lu for introducing to us such a wonderful Dharma Door.

I hope those who come across my sharing will quickly pick up Buddhist scriptures and start practicing Buddhism. In this Age of Dharma Decline, disasters are rampant. Only by practicing Buddhism and reciting scriptures can we free ourselves from suffering and ascend to the Pure Land of Ultimate Bliss!

I take full responsibility for my own karma and will not let others bear it.

Fellow Buddhist Disciple: D107

Fig 1: Practicing Buddhism healed my vitiligo. (A) Before practicing Buddhism. (B). After practicing Buddhism.

Case 2. Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door Cured My Son's Vitiligo

Perhaps the opportunity was right, perhaps the Bodhisattva took pity on me, and in August 2015 I came into contact with Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

My younger sister brought me the Buddhist scriptures from Beijing. She told me that this Little House was a Dharma Gem that could "cure any disease". I felt like I had grasped a hope, and like receiving a treasure. I started to save myself and change my destiny by practicing the Four Golden Buddhist Practices of making vows, performing life liberation, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms!* After six years of diligent practice, my asthma was almost completely cured.

In the second year after practicing Buddhism, a bolt from the blue broke my heart, which disturbed my uneasy life: my son suffered from vitiligo. At that time, I was in pain every day, I couldn't eat, and I couldn't sleep at night. As we all know, vitiligo is a very serious skin disease. There is no particularly effective treatment. Buddhists know that this is actually a karmic disease, that is, a cause-and-effect disease.

My father-in-law was a doctor, who helped women abort, so he created very heavy killing karma. My son's skin disease was my father-in-law's karma retribution. Killing karma can be retributed for 3 generations or more, which is terrible. Therefore, never do killing business.

Since my husband does not believe in Buddhism, he inquired about his friend's treatment plan for this disease. He eventually bought medicine for the child. Meanwhile, I used Buddhism to heal my son's disease by practicing the Four Golden Buddhist Practices. First, I made a vow to recite 108 Little Houses for his karmic creditors and release 800 fish for him. Due to financial constraints and having no job, I could only release a small number of fish. After completing this set of vows, I made another set

of vows. With time, the child's skin disease is improving day by day.

In August 2019, I dreamed that my child's skin disease was not so good. I woke up with cold sweat all over my body. I knew that the number of Little Houses I recited was not enough, and the number of fish I released was not enough. Thus, I vowed again for my child: I would recite 1,000 Little Houses and release 10,000 fish within three years. As long as the child could be cured, no matter how difficult and tired, nothing else mattered. Until August this year, I finished reciting 1,000 Little Houses for his karmic creditors and releasing 10,000 fish for him, a year ahead of schedule.

Please note, that all of these were conducted secretly. This is because when my husband heard me recite the Buddhist scriptures he would be particularly angry. In order to prevent him from creating mouth karma, I could only tolerate it. I had to recite Little Houses secretly and with a low voice. I had to release the fish secretly.

In order to have more money for life release, I need to make money. Previously, I could not work due to my poor health. After practicing Buddhism, my health permitted me to work. The Bodhisattva was so compassionate that She found me a job in a drug store, which was not tiring but earned me more money. Thus, I could have more money to release living creatures. With the money I earned from this job, I could easily fulfill my vow to release living creatures.

If you learn something, you must understand it. If you practice Buddhism, you must believe in it. So long as you are sincere in cultivating your mind, your prayers will be answered! At that time, I listened to my Master's teachings and recordings almost every day. In order to address skin diseases, I would refer to all my Master's teachings and practitioners' cases. It was once that I read one of my Master's instructions

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that was related to skin and bone diseases. The *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots* can be recited 108 times a day to pray for Nanjing Bodhisattva's healing for one month.

Nanjing Bodhisattva is very good at healing. I pray to Nanjing Bodhisattva every day to cure my son's skin disease when I offer incense to Bodhisattvas. A miracle happened. One night, I dreamed that a gentleman came to heal my son. When I woke up the next day, I knew it was the Bodhisattva who had come to heal my son. I felt even more confident that my child's illness would be cured.

Another key point is that no matter who is sick, while you recite Buddhist scriptures for him, he himself must believe in Buddhism. This is so that he can receive our aura and energy to get well faster. My son is very obedient, has an affinity with Buddha and is very kind. He vowed not to eat live sea animals anymore. He also can recite the *Great Compassion Mantra*, and the *Heart Sutra*, and read *Buddhism in Plain Terms*. Hence, we worked together to solve his skin problem.

During this period, I had a bad dream about his skin disease, so I made a vow to recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* 10,000 times for him, to transfer my 2 years' merits and virtues for being a vegetarian to him, and to transfer my 3 years' merits and virtues for propagating Dharma online to him.

All my efforts have not been in vain. The miracle finally appeared: my child's skin recovered health! The Guan Yin Bodhisattva's Citta Dharma Door is true!

Thinking back on my experience of studying Buddhism over the past few years, how many times have I knelt in front of the Buddha in tears, confessing the wrong I had done, begging the Bodhisattva to forgive me, and begging our Bodhisattva to save me and my poor child? As Guan Yin Bodhisattva enlightened us, "I am everywhere if you ask me." Guan Yin Bodhisattva is really compassionate!

I am grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for Her compassionate salvation of me and my son. It is the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door that has given me a second life and given our family hope. I am grateful to my benefactor Master Lu for His compassionate blessing and for saving my spiritual life. I am immensely grateful, and I am grateful every day.

Now, my husband has changed a lot, from the beginning of the opposition to now a little acceptance. He can cook vegetarian food for me. I am really thankful to my husband for providing me with a safe harbor. Although he has not fully accepted Buddhism

until now, I believe that he will believe in the near future. I am grateful for his obstacles to me so that I can be so firm in my faith in learning Buddhism. His adverse condition is my contributory condition. I am grateful to my son for transforming me into a Buddhist in such a way. I am grateful for my illness, which has brought me to Buddhism. I am grateful for all the people and things that have obstructed me, which have further strengthened my mind so that I can believe in the Buddha and the Bodhisattva in a consistent manner!

In the days to come, I will definitely make more efforts to study Buddhism and cultivate my mind, use my own experience to propagate the Dharma, benefit sentient beings, follow in the footsteps of my Master, and form positive connections with all beings, extensively transforming sentient beings!

Presenter: N108

Case 3. The Three Golden Buddhist Practices Cured My Son's Sudden Vitiligo in Just Three Months

In May 2017, my son, a freshman in college, suddenly developed white patches around his mouth, nose, and ears. After a hospital examination, he was diagnosed with vitiligo.

This condition manifests as white patches on the skin, significantly affecting a person's appearance and often leading to feelings of inferiority. My wife and I had been practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door for nearly a year, benefiting greatly from it. We understood that this was a karmic illness caused by our son's past deeds. However, we firmly believed in the boundless power of Buddhism and that the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door could cure his vitiligo.

The Three Golden Buddhist Practices—making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life liberation—are miraculous methods given to us by Guan Yin Bodhisattva to eliminate karma. In May 2017, my wife and I made vows to Guan Yin Bodhisattva:

- (1). I vowed to recite 108 Little Houses for my son's karmic creditors and to release 1,200 fish for him.
- (2). My wife vowed to recite 108 Little Houses for my son's karmic creditors and to spend 3,000 CNY on fish liberation for him.

We sincerely prayed to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva to help our son eliminate his karma and recover soon.

After making the vows, we began fulfilling them. As we started reciting Little Houses for my son's karmic creditors, the white patches on his face initially

increased, and new ones appeared. Despite this, we persisted in fulfilling our vows. When we had recited nearly 100 Little Houses for his karmic creditors and released over 1,000 fish, we could visibly see the effects of karma elimination through the Three Golden Buddhist Practices. The white patches on my son's face darkened, and his skin tone gradually returned to normal.

After my wife completed her initial 108 Little Houses, she made a second vow to recite another batch of seven at a time. We continued to fulfill our vows. By the time my wife had recited approximately 140 Little Houses and I had recited around 120, totaling about 260 sheets, and we had released more than 2,000 fish, the Three Golden Buddhist Practices produced remarkable results. By August of that same year, the white patches on my son's face had almost disappeared, and his skin had largely returned to normal. He looked no different from anyone else.

My wife and I witnessed the miracle created by making vows, reciting scriptures, and performing life liberation—something that modern medicine could hardly achieve. The Three Golden Buddhist Practices are undeniably effective, restoring our son's clear and clean appearance!

As our son's condition stabilized, we continued to recite Little Houses for his karmic creditors and perform life liberation for him intermittently to strengthen and consolidate his recovery. Seven years have passed since then, and he remains perfectly healthy. The power of Buddhism is extraordinary—this karmic entanglement causing sudden vitiligo on his face was resolved in just 3 months.

Moreover, this incident subtly influenced our son to embrace Buddhism. He has now begun practicing daily recitations and performing Buddhist practices himself. With the blessings of Buddhism, he enjoys good health, a smooth career, positive connections, and Dharma joy. We are deeply grateful to the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door!

Vitiligo is one of the world's most challenging conditions to cure, with even wealthy or famous individuals unable to overcome it. However, Buddhism can resolve both physical and mental health problems. As long as we sincerely make vows, recite scriptures, perform life liberation, study *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, and repent to eliminate karma, even so-called incurable diseases can be healed, benefiting ourselves and others while bringing happiness to the whole family.

Since practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, I have experienced countless spiritual benefits.

Buddhism in Plain Terms has helped me understand cause and effect, break through delusions, find peace, and achieve liberation from suffering. The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is a righteous Dharma that aligns with modern times. Guan Yin Bodhisattva is omnipresent, granting help to all who pray sincerely. I hope that those destined to hear my story will not hesitate or delay but take action now. Start reciting Buddhist scriptures early, and you will benefit early.

Fellow practitioner: S109

Case 4. The Three Golden Buddhist Practices Cured My Vitiligo for Over 30 Years

When I was 14 years old, patches of white spots began appearing on my skin. The hospital diagnosed it as vitiligo. At that moment, I was so frightened by the doctor's words that I burst into tears. However, I clung to the hope that it might just be an ordinary skin condition.

By the time I turned 25, the doctor's warning had come true. My forehead, the area between my eyebrows, my hands, back, and legs were covered with mysterious spots. Overnight, my face became blotchy, resembling a patchwork. These spots on my body and face severely affected my appearance. At 25, when most people were enjoying the prime of their lives, I was struggling with this condition. It delayed my marriage until the age of 30. Even after marriage, my husband was repulsed by my condition, and our relationship remained cold and distant.

When I was 43, I suffered a medical mishap during an abortion procedure. The doctor said I had only a one-in-ten-thousand chance of surviving, and even if I did survive, I would be disabled. At that moment, I firmly believed in the existence of Guan Yin Bodhisattva. I kept silently praying, "Guan Yin Bodhisattva, please save me!"

The compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva heard my plea and saved me—it was a miracle!

I survived. However, after recovering from this severe illness, my husband divorced me, leaving my life in shambles.

When one door closes, another one opens. That life-altering illness became a turning point for me, as it led me to discover Buddhism. I am deeply grateful to my spiritual guide, Dharma practitioner X, who shared Buddhist scriptures and the DVDs of Master Lu's Dharma talks with me. Watching Master Lu's teachings and listening to the experiences shared by other practitioners filled me with hope and encouragement.

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One particular story deeply resonated with me—a fellow practitioner, whose experience was strikingly similar to mine, had her vitiligo completely healed by reciting Little Houses. Her health also improved significantly! Inspired by her story, I resolutely stepped into the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and eagerly began practicing, including performing my daily recitations and reciting Little Houses.

In 2018, I was fortunate enough to attend the Singapore Dharma Conference. During the event, I made the following vows:

- (1). Recite 800 Little Houses for my karmic creditors;
- (2). Release 2,500 fish (later increased to 5,000);
- (3). Share my story of recovery. Vow to never stop reciting scriptures, releasing lives, or helping others;
- (4). Dedicate 50% of the merits and virtues from attending the Singapore Dharma Conference to eliminating the karmic debts behind my vitiligo.

After making these vows, I focused wholeheartedly on releasing lives and reciting Little Houses. When I had completed over 500 Little Houses, a miracle occurred. The white patches on my face and body began to fade, and the hair on my hands started turning black again! Through the application of the Three Golden Buddhist Practices—making vows, reciting scriptures, and releasing lives—my vitiligo, which had tormented me for over 30 years, was nearly healed. I could finally wear short-sleeved clothes in summer again.

The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door restored my confidence and transformed me into a new person. I am endlessly grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva, to Master Lu, and to the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door!

Since practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, my life has become increasingly smooth, and my career has flourished.

Through my story, I want to tell everyone that the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is truly extraordinary. The Three Golden Buddhist Practices are incredibly effective! As long as we sincerely recite scriptures, make vows, release lives, and study *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, we can transform our destinies!

Fellow Practitioner: Y110

Case 5. Two Decades of Pain and Suffering Relieved—Blessings from Bodhisattva Freed Me from the Misery of Vitiligo

Over 20 years ago, due to ignorance and lack of wisdom, I created heavy karmic debts. I deeply repent before the Bodhisattva. Looking back, I regret that in my pursuit to escape poverty, I started a small-scale livestock business in my hometown, raising pigs and

chickens. Although the scale was modest, it generated slightly more income compared to farming.

About a year after I began this business, one day, I suddenly noticed a few tiny white spots on my face. I immediately went to see a doctor, who prescribed medication for two days. However, shortly after, white spots began to appear on my forehead as well. Why was it that the more medication I took, the more the white spots spread? I decided to visit a major hospital in the city for a thorough examination.

Over the next ten-plus years, I sought various treatments and tried every possible remedy, from TCM to Western medicine. My condition fluctuated but never truly improved. The medication I consumed left me with a weak spleen and stomach; whatever I ate, my body failed to digest properly. Eventually, my immune system deteriorated, and by 2015, I became seriously ill and was hospitalized.

From 2015 to 2016, I was unable to work and became allergic to nearly everything I ate [11]. I spent every day in restlessness and distress. In the latter half of 2016, I was fortunate to encounter Buddhism and began learning how to recite Buddhist scriptures. That marked the turning point in my life.

In *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, Vol. 1, Chapter 34, Master Lu enlightened us that: “If one commits killing karma, its repercussions can affect 3-4 generations. The heavier the karma, the greater and longer the impact on future generations.” It was only then that I realized my illness was caused by the karmic debts stemming from killing. I felt as if awakened from a dream, and tears streamed down like a fountain. The Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu gave me, the ignorant child, the chance to encounter the Dharma and begin the journey of liberation.

Knowing the severity of my karmic debts, I relied entirely on the compassion of the Bodhisattva to help me eliminate them. I dedicated myself to daily scripture recitation, performing life liberation, offering Little Houses to my karmic creditors, helping others, and engaging in Dharma propagation, never slacking for a moment. I vowed to stay true to my original aspiration and diligently practice Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door only. Occasionally, I even went out alone to spread the Dharma and form positive affinities with others.

I had stopped running the livestock business three years after starting it and then left the country. In 2023, I returned to China to celebrate the New Year with my elderly parents and mother-in-law. One night during the lunar twelfth month, I stayed with my sister

at a local inn in our hometown. That night, I dreamt of a doctor in a white coat who was treating my sister. I asked the doctor to examine me as well. The doctor lifted my bangs and said, "Your forehead is completely white-111..."

Upon waking, I made a vow to recite 111 Little Houses for my karmic creditors and 111 times the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* to repent for my karmic debts. I prayed to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to help me repent and eliminate the karmic obstacles related to my vitiligo. I promised to share my recovery experience to help guide others and bring them to the Dharma Door once my condition improved.

By 2024, I had returned overseas and completed my vow of offering 111 Little Houses. On one occasion, while spreading the Dharma alone, I encountered a kind young lady. Upon seeing the vitiligo on my face, she recommended a reasonably priced medication for me to try. One treatment course cost only a little over 200 CNY (~\$28).

I am incredibly grateful for Guan Yin Bodhisattva's compassion! That kind young lady seemed like the Nirmanakaya of Guan Yin Bodhisattva Herself. The medication she recommended began to show results within about 20 days. After 2-3 months, most of the white spots on my face had disappeared. My skin became healthier and more radiant [**Figure 2**].

After over 20 years, I finally have a presentable face again. Although the spots on other parts of my body have yet to fully heal, I firmly believe that, with the blessings of the Bodhisattva, I will recover completely soon! Such an incredible experience full of Dharma joy—I couldn't wait to share it!

Since encountering the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door,

I have experienced countless miraculous events. I am profoundly grateful to the great Guan Yin Bodhisattva and our great Master Lu! The power of Buddhism is boundless. Practicing Buddhism, reciting scriptures, and cultivating the mind have improved my health, life, and family in every way. I am immensely grateful to have encountered the Dharma. Many issues that seem impossible to resolve in daily life can indeed be resolved through Buddhism.

Dear readers, as long as you believe in Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu, have unwavering faith and diligently apply the Five Golden Buddhist Practices, remain steadfast in cultivating without expecting anything in return, you will certainly reap unimaginable rewards!

Guan Yin Bodhisattva, with boundless compassion, responds to all sincere prayers and rescues all in distress. The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is real, efficacious, and extraordinary. The moment you pick up the Buddhist scripture and begin practicing Buddhism is the moment you start transforming your destiny.

I hope my story inspires more sentient beings to stop killing. The law of cause and effect is the No. 1 law of the universe. Those who harm life today will inevitably face retribution in the future. I conclude with Master Lu's teaching from *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, Vol. 1, Chapter 34: "We must take responsibility for our descendants, accumulate merits and virtue, and do good deeds. Do not commit wrongdoing, especially killing karma."

I will bear my own karmic consequences and will not let others bear them for me.

Fellow Dharma Practitioner: W17

Fig 2: Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door healed my face vitiligo. (A) Before practicing Buddhism. (B). After practicing Buddhism. Photo B was taken in February 2025.

Case 6. Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door Cured My Vitiligo and Frozen Shoulder

In the summer of 2015, the darkest year of my life, I was diagnosed with vitiligo. Initially, my friend inadvertently saw that my mouth corners were whitish and different from normal skin. My friend advised me to go to the hospital for a checkup. At first, I thought it was a cold food lump and didn't take it seriously. Later, I looked in the mirror for a long time. I felt something was wrong, so I headed to a TCM Hospital to check. I was diagnosed with vitiligo, which is very difficult to treat.

I was blinded. How could it be? No one in our family has had this disease. How could I get it? I searched the internet like crazy. The more I looked, the more anxious I felt. It is commonly known as immortal cancer. It spreads to the whole face or even the whole body. I was afraid of becoming like that. I was helpless and scared. I broke down.

I quit my job because I was afraid my face would scare my colleagues. I didn't know what to do. I lived in panic every day. It feels like a leaking house facing a rainy night. One trouble follows another. My left arm is unknowingly sore. I can't lift it up. It is even more painful behind my back. Especially at night, I could not sleep at all. Each nerve in my arm is like a needle prick, which makes it difficult to sleep. I was 39 years old. Why did misfortune suddenly strike me? What did I do wrong? I travelled to a hospital in another city and had an MRI. The report showed that it was scapular effusion, and there was no good treatment other than exercise.

Just when I was lost, I encountered the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. I am grateful to Bodhisattva. I think now, I may be quite honest and still have a little kindness in my heart. Bodhisattva took pity on me and let me meet Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. When I walked to the park to exercise, I ran into Buddhist practitioners who were also exercising. I thought it might be healthy and helpful for my body, so I followed them. The first thing they talked about every day was their daily recitations. I felt curious. Buddhist practitioner H was in the seventies. I was wondering what kind of recitation H was doing at such an old age. Hence, I asked them what their recitations were. This question led me to join Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

They said Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door could save me from my illness. I immediately expressed a strong interest in practicing it. When I got a book H offered me, and carefully opened it, I was deeply impressed by the pictures of Master Lu inside. It is because

Master Lu created a different path for my future life.

I held Buddhist scriptures in both hands, looking at the corresponding effects of each scripture. It turned out that each Buddhist scripture was a medicine prescription. When I recited the *Heart Sutra* and the *Eighty-eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, I howled and cried. I realized how much bad karma I had created. I thought I was a good person, but now I realize that I was not even qualified to be a human being at that time. I killed, I aborted, I committed sexual misconduct, I was delusional, I had everything. That is why I got vitiligo and a frozen shoulder. It's all my self-made causes. I deeply repent here. I am sorry, please forgive me for my ignorance.

After a week of daily recitations, I proceeded to make a vow for a set of 49 Little Houses to repay my miscarried child. Later on, I repaid another set of Little Houses to my own karmic creditors. After about 100 Little Houses were repaid, my frozen shoulder was significantly better. What is even more amazing is that vitiligo is turning around as well.

In January 2016 I set up a Buddhist altar at my home. On that day, I made a vow to become a vegetarian, and never kill living beings.

Physically, I used to have pain here and there. Especially with my back and frozen shoulder, I had to go to acupuncture every week. Now I haven't undergone massage and acupuncture, and my frozen shoulder has basically recovered, and my back hasn't recurred.

In terms of mindset, I used to blame everybody but myself, have low self-confidence and constant afflictions. I would be sad for days about a trivial thing. Now that I have studied Buddhism, I realize that everything is cause and effect. It's all my fault.

Behaviorally, I used to be fond of eating and averse to work. Now that I have learned the Buddhism. I take the initiative to do things, and I can help others.

As the saying says, if you study Buddhism for one year, the Buddha is in front of you. If you study Buddhism for three years, the Buddha is in the sky. In the first year, I was quite diligent every day in order to get better quickly, and I was a different person than I used to be.

However, with time, I slacked off. Because I did not practice Buddhism diligently, my inherent flaws flared up and I lost my temper. This led to me that I could only recite 3 Little Houses a day. In the summer of 2017, vitiligo returned. Unlike the first time, this time the disease spread to the eyes, eyebrows, and neck. My heart, which had been clearer, turned confused again. I can't find the direction. I also often get

pedantic in my Buddhism study and often wonder if there is something wrong with the Dharma. Especially since I have been studying the Dharma for two years, why doesn't the Bodhisattva bless me?

My situation continued to fluctuate until I attended the Indonesian Buddhist Conference. Fortunately, Bodhisattva helped me again, allowing me to attend the Buddhist Conference and become a disciple of Master Lu. At the ceremony, I couldn't even make a sound when I was stuck in my throat by the spirit. I could only keep shedding tears. Master Lu was leading the reading of the *Disciple's Code* in front of me, but I couldn't read it properly, letting the tears spill out like crazy. My karmic obstacles are so deep. I didn't make any effort to eliminate my karma, and now I let Master Lu carry my karma. I sincerely apologize to the Bodhisattva and Master Lu. Many people at the ceremony saw a remarkable sight, but I didn't. I'm really not cultivating well!

During the Buddhist Conference, I received guidance from a Buddhist practitioner, Mr. W. He said I had not progressed in my cultivation. He pointed out my shortcomings and reminded me of precautions to take in my future cultivation. I am really grateful to him, who was really sent by the Bodhisattva to enlighten me. After I returned from the Buddhist Conference, I felt completely new and rekindled my motivation to study Buddhism. I adjusted my goals, mainly eliminating karma first, and made a vow to recite 500 Little Houses to my karmic creditors during the year. I made a vow to recite the *Eighty-eight Buddhas Great Repentance* according to the Ten Meritorious Deeds standard to repent of wrongdoings and refrain from doing them in this life.

Now, the vitiligo on my face is largely invisible. Around my eyes, I noticed melanin covering my once-white skin slightly. I know it was the Bodhisattva who saved me again. I am grateful to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, and to Master Lu for silently blessing me. I make a vow that I will follow Master Lu to practice well, let go of the 'lesser self' and attain the 'greater self', and be a good helper of Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu, promote Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and save sentient beings.

Throughout my experience of learning Buddhism, I summarize the detours I have taken on my way to learning Buddhism:

(1). Insincerity of the heart. I know very well that practicing Buddhism is cultivating one's heart. If one does not have true faith in the Dharma and Guan Yin Bodhisattva, it is useless. Only if you give your heart wholeheartedly to Guan Yin Bodhisattva will you be

saved!

(2). My will is not firm. My will is not strong enough, that is to say, it is not refined enough. Why is it not refined? To put it bluntly, the power of a vow is not sufficient. I prayed with a purpose before. So once my target was achieved, I slacked off.

(3). Shortcomings were not overcome. When I want to lose my temper, I still lose my temper. When I feel afflicted, I still feel afflicted. Here I think of a way to turn my mind. It is also what Master Lu always talks about, turning afflictions into Bodhi. In our lives, we must change practically, and only when we change can we progress.

(4). Lack of action. This action is related to vow power. Usually in Buddha's study and worship, I made empty vows, and I did not go to do it. Slowly the heart is numb. By the time karmic obstacles flare up, it's too late to regret.

Presenter: Z111

Discussion

Vitiligo, an autoimmune disorder characterized by depigmented skin patches, has long been a subject of scientific investigation. Although TCM claims to be effective in treating vitiligo [25, 26], truly curative reports are rare. Western medicine has delved deeply into the molecular mechanisms of vitiligo, identifying depigmentation of the skin as the primary cause. However, it has yet to provide a definitive cure. This suggests that neither approach has fully grasped the essence of vitiligo. Their understanding remains confined to the symptomatic level. This limitation has led to the exploration of alternative approaches, including spiritual perspectives.

The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door emphasizes the karmic and spiritual aspects of diseases such as vitiligo. According to this practice, medically incurable illnesses may stem from karmic debts or spiritual disturbances. Karmic and spiritual ailments require karmic and spiritual methods for treatment. By reciting Buddhist scriptures, such as the *Heart Sutra*, *Great Compassion Mantra*, and *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, one can help eliminate negative karma and enhance positive energy. Additionally, offering Little Houses to repay spirits' karmic debts can aid in their ascension, thereby alleviating physical symptoms. This approach has demonstrated effectiveness in addressing mental illnesses [27], neurological disorders [28, 29], and autoimmune diseases [11, 29].

This study expands the scope of medically incurable conditions treatable through Buddhist practices by adding vitiligo, a previously classified incurable skin

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disease, to the list of diseases considered curable from a Buddhist perspective.

Except Cases 3 and 4 they did not disclose their source of karma, Cases 1, 2, 5 and 6 all reported their karma sources.

In Case 1, D107 has killed chickens, ducks, and fish. In Case 2, the boy's grandfather worked in a hospital performing abortions. In Case 5, W17 was engaged in animal farming for 2-3 years. In Case 6, Z111 was involved in abortion, killing, and sexual misconduct.

Their occurrence of vitiligo aligns with Master Lu's teachings (Q&A 1-10), which explain that skin diseases are often caused by killing karma [11-14]. Previous reports have indicated that performing abortions can lead to karmic consequences, such as a medical professional herself developing illnesses like leukemia [11]. In this study, the karmic retribution from the grandfather's abortion profession was observed in the grandson, further supporting Master Lu's teaching that killing karma can manifest across 3 generations. In addition to vitiligo, W17 also suffered from food allergies, which were resolved through the practice of Buddhism, as documented in a previous report [11].

For Case 6, Z111 committed multiple wrongdoings that violated the Dharma precepts, resulting in the accumulation of heavy karmic obstacles. Neglecting Dharma practices will allow unresolved karma to resurface, leading to a recurrence of vitiligo. Therefore, those burdened with severe karmic obstacles are not in a position to be negligent in using Dharma to eliminate karma and repay karmic debts. Diligent Buddhist practice is the only option.

Master Lu has enlightened us that: "When you are in the sea of suffering, karma clings to you like a shark. The moment you try to break free from it, the shark will not let you go. No matter where you swim, it will follow closely behind. Even when you finally catch sight of the shore and struggle desperately to reach it, hoping to escape the grasp of karma, it will drag you back down like a relentless shark pulling you by the leg [30]."

Therefore, it is best to avoid creating negative karma. Once karma is formed, it must be resolved; otherwise, no matter how one struggles in the sea of karmic suffering, escape remains impossible. The cycle of rebirth within the Six Realms will persist endlessly [11]. The occurrence of vitiligo and other incurable diseases, as well as their manifestation and healing through Dharma practice, once again affirm Master Lu's enlightenment that *one's own actions determine their karmic consequences* (善惡果報, 唯人自招).

The successful recovery from vitiligo in this study further validates the principles of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door while also underscoring the limitations of medical science in addressing this condition. Thus, it is crucial for medical professionals to develop a deeper understanding of Dharma.

When compared to other skin diseases such as eczema, psoriasis, chronic urticaria, and dyshidrosis, vitiligo differs in that it does not cause physical symptoms like itching, pain, or bleeding. However, it inflicts significant psychological harm. For instance, in Case 6, the patient quit her job out of fear that her facial appearance would frighten her colleagues. This aligns with Master Lu's teaching on patient psychology (Q&A 3), both literally and figuratively.

This example reinforces the idea that human beings must adhere not only to human laws but also to the laws of heaven and the underworld [11]. Violating human laws results in punishment under human justice while breaking the laws of heaven and the underworld incurs consequences from those realms. To avoid transgressing these laws, one should observe the Dharma precepts [11].

Therefore, in addition to addressing physical and emotional needs, spiritual health is essential for comprehensive patient care. This approach enables patients to identify the root cause of their condition and actively work to eliminate it, achieving lasting health.

Despite the success of Dharma in alleviating vitiligo alone, Master Lu advocates a holistic approach and emphasizes the importance of following doctors' advice. In fact, the patients in Cases 1 and 5 were healed through a combination of Dharma practices and medical treatment. Similar outcomes have been observed in the treatment of dyshidrosis [14]. These observations suggest that once karma is removed, medicine can fully exert its potential effect. Therefore, eliminating karma is fundamental, as also observed by Dharma practitioner N43 in treating her son's autism [31].

While further research is needed to scientifically validate the spiritual methods of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door on a large scale, their potential to complement conventional treatments warrants exploration. Integrating spiritual and medical practices may help patients attain not only physical healing but also emotional and spiritual well-being.

Conclusion

Vitiligo is a karmic disease that manifests with symptoms such as autoimmune dysfunction, often leading to significant psychological distress. While

conventional treatments focus on managing symptoms and achieving varying degrees of repigmentation, they often fail to provide a permanent cure. In contrast, the holistic approach of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door addresses the root cause—karma—yielding results that conventional medicine cannot match.

This study reinforces our previous findings that skin diseases have a karmic origin. Therefore, eliminating negative karma is essential for true healing. The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door has demonstrated effectiveness in curing vitiligo, just as it has in treating other skin diseases. Furthermore, it validates the truth of Master Lu's teachings.

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Conflict of Interest

No.

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Ethical Statement

The author did not involve any part of the experimental design, experimental treatments and result analysis of the patient. All the experimental procedures and practices by the presenter were done by himself independently.

Statement by Translator and Writer

The 6 stories and 10 Q&As in the text were translated from Chinese to English based on their intended meaning rather than a word-for-word approach. The remaining portions of the paper were written based on my limited understanding of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. If there are any inaccuracies or deviations from the true meaning of the Chinese version, or if the content does not accurately reflect Master Lu's teachings, I sincerely seek forgiveness from the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, all Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, Dharma Protectors, and Master Jun Hong Lu.

Disclaimer of Liability

The contents of the presentation, comments, and discussion, including text, images, and other information obtained from Dharma practitioners, are provided strictly for reference purposes. Due to the unique nature of individual karma, results similar to those experienced by the practitioner may not be replicated. The experiences and advice shared should not be construed as medical advice or a

diagnosis.

In the event of an emergency, it is crucial to promptly contact your doctor or emergency services by dialing 911. Relying on any information found in this paper is done solely at your own risk. The author bears no responsibility for the consequences. By using or misusing the contents, you accept liability for any personal injury, including death. It is imperative to exercise caution and seek professional medical guidance for health-related concerns.

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